

THE ECONOMICALLY ACTIVE POPULATION, THE LABOUR FORCE, AND EMPLOYMENT/UNEMPLOYMENT IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Key Indicators of the Labour Market, KILMs serve as the tool for monitoring and assessing current realities in the world of work by addressing the many pertinent Labour Market (LM) questions which is a requisite for the development of informed, effective labour-related strategies at all levels. The paper conducts a critical analysis of the Nigerian Labour Market based on 3 KILMS, the economically active population (EAP), labour force, and (un)employment in a bid to evaluate the LM functioning while also briefly discussing the factors giving rise to the observed performance or non-performance. Data used were sourced from secondary sources, primarily government publications and data from the National Bureau of Statistics.

It was found that the high birth and fertility rate of Nigeria has led to a huge EAP dominated by dependents, and congestion of the LM with oversupply labour leading to a high unemployment rate of 33.3%. Gender ascriptiveness issues are also evident, with females recording a significantly lower labour force figure and participation rate, while the employment and underemployment rate was much higher despite balanced involvement with regards to the EAP.

To turn around the distasteful situation, the paper recommends that government: supports the informal sector that can absorb many of the unemployed, provide a sound infrastructural environment to attract investment, conduct cautionary considerations of technological policies before adoption, among others.

1. INTRODUCTION

Any organization, institution, or government that advocates labour-related strategies needs relevant data to monitor and assess current realities in the world of work. This makes it imperative to engage in regular data collection programs to improve the dissemination of data on key elements of the labour market.

The Key Indicators of the Labour Market (KILM) function as tools in the examination and evaluation of several germane situations related to the functioning of labour markets. For some context, well-built evidence-informed policy-making relies not only on best practices in the labour market but also inefficiencies such as labour underutilization. As such, in designing employment policies aimed at enhancing the well-being of workers while also fostering economic growth, and in cognizance of a broad view of the world of work, comprehensive collection, organization, and analysis of labour market information is pertinent. The KILMs in this view serve as a tool in addressing the many pertinent questions relating to the labour market by identifying where labour is underutilized, where decent work is lacking, underemployment, labour productivity, and identification of best practices. KILMs can also aid the assessment of employment in a globalizing world by enabling employment dynamics associated with globalization to be monitored especially in the areas of its impact on job loss and creations and on changes in wages and productivity.

The paper examines three key labour indicators of the market i.e. the economically active population, labour force, and (un)employment by reviewing data sourced from secondary sources to evaluate the performance of the Nigerian labour market and pin-point factors giving rise to its performance or non-performance, also to inform the work of policymakers and the government.

2. THE ECONOMICALLY ACTIVE POPULATION, LABOUR FORCE, EMPLOYMENT AND UNEMPLOYMENT IN NIGERIA

2.1 Economically Active Population

The economically active population encompasses all persons of either sex supplying labour for production of goods and services during a defined period. It covers all persons between the ages of 15 - 64 who furnish their labour for the production of economic goods and services and includes workers formerly or informally employed, the self-employed, employers, and the unemployed wishing to work.

The number of persons in the economically active population in the course of the Q4, 2020 Nigeria Bureau of Statistics - NBS survey was 122,049,400 which is higher than the figure recorded in Q2, 2020 (116,871,186) by 4.3%. Females represent 50.49% of the economically active population while the males account for 49.5%.

With reference to age groups, 30.2% of the total active population is within the ages of 15 -24, the highest amidst the age groupings, while the age group with the smallest active population is 55-64 with 10,221,108 (8.37%) of the total active population. Also, of this number, females represent 50.49%, while males account for 49.5%.

Distribution of Working Population by AGE & SEX			
Age -Group	Male	Female	Total
15-24	18,380,640	18,483,275	36,863,915
25-34	13,625,712	17,982,769	31,608,481
35-44	12,759,156	12,791,331	25,550,488
45-54	9,868,444	7,936,964	17,805,408
55-64	5,787,790	4,433,318	10,221,108
Total	60,421,742	61,627,657	122,049,400

Source: Nigeria Bureau of Statistics

2.2 Labour Force

The labour force refers to people within ages 15 -64, who are able and willing to work. In conformance to the standards of definition specified by the International Labour Organization. It encompasses persons currently employed and those that are unemployed but seeking work as well as first-time job-seekers. However, not everyone who works is included as unpaid workers, family workers, and students are often omitted, and some countries do not count members of the armed forces.

It is the estimated number of persons within the economically active population or working population that is available and willing to work. Persons in the economically active population who are neither employed nor unemployed are considered as not being in the labour force. This residual category (that are not in the labour force) includes people who: - are retired; attend educational institutions; are permanently unable to work due to physical or mental disabilities ;have personal or family responsibilities such as unpaid housework and childcare; were temporarily unavailable for work in the survey reference week, and are not actively seeking work.

The NBS estimated the number of persons in the labour force (within ages 15-64 able and willing to work) to be 69,675,468 implying that only 57.09% of Nigeria's economically active population are in the labour force. Another key observation is that unlike in the economically active population, those within the age bracket of 25-34 are the highest, with 20,091,695 or 28.8% of the labour force. That persons within the age group of 15-24 are involved in one form of schooling or the other, hence are not willing and/or available for work should explain that. Also, while females are more dominant under the active population, the reverse holds for the labour force, with males accounting for 56.72%, and females accounting for 43.28%.

Source:

Source: Nigeria Bureau of Statistics

Labour Force - Q4, 2020			
Educational Qualification		Age-Group	
None	20,652,597	15-24	9,853,103
First School Leaving Certificate	9,240,842	25-34	20,091,695
Middle School Leaving Certificate	326,025	35-44	19,268,957
Vocational/Commercial	233,535	45-54	13,302,064
Junior Secondary School Certificate	3,351,293	55-64	7,159,648
Senior Secondary School Certificate	22,031,170	Gender	
A' levels	748,228	Male	39,523,050
NCE/OND/Nursing	5,779,243	Female	30,152,418
BA/BSc/HND	5,940,546	Place of Residence	
Tech/Prof	187,033	Urban	26,459,732
Masters	349,306	Rural	43,215,736
Doctorate	73,859	Total	69,675,468
others (specify)	761,792		

Source: Nigeria Bureau of Statistics

2.2.1 Labour Force Participation Rate

Labour force participation rate refers to the percentage of the population of working age furnishing their labour for the production of economic goods and services whether formally employed or not. It is the measure of the proportion of the population that engages actively in the labour market, it indicates the relative size of the supply of labour available to engage in the production of goods and services.

Labour Force Participation Rate is expressed as:

$$(Labour\ force) / (Working\ Age\ Population) \times 100$$

2.3 Employment and Unemployment

The ILO defines employment as the number of people persons 15 years and older who during a specified brief period (e.g. seven days) have worked for five or more hours for a wage, or salary or for-profit or family gain, in cash or kind.

Under-employment is a situation whereby persons are in employment that entails less than normal hours of work. Under-employment can be of two types which are visible and invisible. Visible refers to involuntary underemployment while visible is a case of underutilization of skills or situation where one is working below his/her skill level. Unemployment on the other hand is a situation where a person that is available for work, willing to work, and seeking work is without work or has not been able to find work. A person aged 16-50 ready and willing to work but has no work is said to be unemployed and according to the ILO, a person is said to be employed if he has worked a total of 40hrs a week. As such, someone who works less than 20hours a week is underemployed. The unemployment rate is expressed as:

$$(Unemployed\ population) / (Labour\ Force\ Population) \times 100$$

Employment is one of the most important social and economic issues in every country and achieving full employment is even more important in developing countries like Nigeria where unemployment and underemployment have been a major source and outcome of widespread poverty. Despite the exaggerated electioneering promises of the political class, the achievement of decent employment and impressive growth remains an illusion. High rates of employment, poverty and similar miseries are the order of the day in Nigeria of today with a rate of 33.3% or 23.2 million Nigerians of about 70 million people in the labour force while underemployment

is at 22.8%. This is really unpleasant particularly considering that in normal labour markets, the level of unemployment is supposed to be about 4-6 %.

Furthermore, a mash-up of both the unemployment and underemployment rates for the reference period resulted in 56.1%. The implication is that 33.3% of the labour force in Nigeria or 23,187,389 persons either did nothing or worked for less than 20 hours a week, and as such are unemployed going by the Nigerian definition. Using the international definition of unemployment (ILO's standard of 1-hour work per week), Nigeria's recent unemployment rate is 17.5%. Comparing this rate internationally, of 181 countries with rates published within the last 2 years, Nigeria currently ranks as the 19th country with the highest unemployment rate. Some of the other countries with very high unemployment rates are Bosnia and Herzegovinian (33.7%), Namibia (33.4%), and South Africa (32.5%) while those with the lowest rates are Qatar (0.1%), Belarus (0.2%), Niger (0.3%) and Myanmar (0.7%).

Analysis from the educational status perspective shows that the economic growth of Nigeria is not keeping pace with the educational output, with those with A 'levels as their highest qualification recording the highest rate of unemployment with 50.7%, those with first degrees/HND followed closely at 40.1%. Doctorate Degree holders reported the lowest rate of unemployment at 16.9% during the reference period. Under the age-groupings, the highest rate of unemployment was recorded among the 15-24year age-group with 53.4%, followed by those aged between 25-34years with 37.0%, together the youth population recorded an unemployment rate of 42.5%.

In the case of underemployment by age grouping, those aged between 55 -64years recorded an underemployment rate of 25.7%, the highest amongst the age groups. This was followed by those aged between 45-54years with 24.4% while those with the lowest underemployment rate were those aged between 15-24years with 19.8%. A combination of unemployment and underemployment rates shows that those aged between 15 -24years reported a combined rate of 73.2%, showing a serious challenge for the age group in securing full-time employment.

Female unemployment was higher between the genders with 35.2% while male was 31.8% during the reference period. A similar case was recorded for underemployment, 24.2% was reported for females, while males reported an underemployment rate of 21.8%. Among rural dwellers, unemployment rate was put at 34.5%, while it was 31.3% for urban dwellers. For underemployment, the rate for rural dwellers was 26.9%, while that of urban dwellers was 16.2%.

3.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

3.1 Discussion

Nothing exemplifies the astronomic population growth of Nigeria better than the huge size of its economically active population. For the reference period, 2020, the birth rate for Nigeria was 37 per 1000 people while the fertility rate was 5.2 births per woman leading to a population growth rate of 2.5% as against the previous year. The attendant consequence is the 122million people in the economically active population which is on the high side, especially when compared to that of fellow developing African countries such as Ghana with a birth rate of 3.8 per woman and 13.7million people in its Economically Active Population. South Africa has an EAP of 39.4million. Also, that only 57.09% of Nigeria's EAP is in the labour force indicates the vast majority of the EAP such as the 15-24years age group that constitutes 30.2% of the EAP are not actively involved in the labour market and largely still dependents. Both genders also seem to be balanced in terms of representation in the EAP.

However, looking at the labour force, the females are less dominant with 43.3% against 56.7% of the male gender, this is due to the gender ascriptiveness issues in the labour market which is discouraging and limiting female participation in the Nigerian LM. The 25-34years age group also dominated as labour market activity is key here unlike EAP which allowed coverage of students and other such groups. At a labour force size of 69.6million, compared to 12.9million in Ghana and 21.7million in South Africa, the Nigerian labour force can be said to be oversaturated with the huge size of the supply of labour available to engage in the production of goods and services. The absorptive capacity of the labour market is however unimpressive with the labour market participation rate at 53.43% compared to neighboring Ghana's 66.2%. This is because the economic growth is not keeping pace with the educational output as the institutions are producing more graduates at all levels than the economy can absorb. This is evident in the unemployment data showing 50.7% of the unemployed hold advanced level diplomas while 40.1% hold higher degrees.

The foregoing, coupled with other factors such as economic hardships occasioned by fall in crude oil prices on account of falling global demand, the effects of conflicts and crime such as the Boko-haram, bandits, kidnapping, and herder-farmer crisis on discouraging investments which could have otherwise generated employment opportunities, the devaluation of the naira and several series of structural adjustment programs taken on by the State since the 1980s which led to the loss of several jobs through retrenchments as well as making it difficult for many manufacturers to source imports in form of the raw materials required for industrial production

has led Nigeria to its current state of massive unemployment with a 33.3% rate i.e. over 23million and 1 in 3 of the labour force unemployed. The lack of support for the informal sector with the capacity to support, poor infrastructural environment, and technological policies that are not mindful of the high population rate of the country are other factors giving rise to the high rate of unemployment in Nigeria.

The high rate of unemployment has attendant effects such as increased crimes rates and youth restiveness which many eerie youths might otherwise divert their energy towards. Other implications are a rise in unfair labour practice with the tendency to increase casualization and contract workers as well as the tendency of wage not commensurating effort. Employers may fix wages unilaterally without recourse to equilibrium wage due to a large supply of labour than its demand in the labour market.

3.2 Conclusion and Recommendations

With the paper centering on the functioning of the Nigerian labour market by examining key variables that give indications of LM functioning, it becomes evident that the Nigerian labour market space is congested and plagued with a problem of a oversupply of labour that are capable, willing and available to engage in productive work i.e. production of goods and services. The irony however is that these jobs are not available as the socio-economic environment has made it difficult for investments to flow and the industry to thrive, leading to a terrible unemployment situation which hit a record low in the fourth quarter of the year 2020 at 33.3%. To improve on the situation the paper suggests:

- Provision of a sound infrastructural environment by the government energy such as internet services, good road networks, and energy to stimulate entrepreneurship and enterprise and drive foreign direct investments. Also, the informal sector which predominantly accounts for more than 60 percent of economic activities in the urban areas also has the capacity to absorb many of the unemployed provided government will support with initiatives such as credit facilities and small business-friendly policies
- Technological policies in Nigeria need to be mindful of the high population rate of the country. Digitalization which may affect employment and unemployment should be given cautionary consideration on their effect on employment and job retention. For a country with a high population like Nigeria, job displacing technology and equipment should be discouraged while job creation technologies should be encouraged. A good example is a comparison between GSM mobile phones and ATMs (Automated Teller

Machines). While ATMs displaced a lot of workers in the banking industry, swelling the pool of the unemployed, GSM on the other hand created jobs

- The government should pay keen and sincere attention to the fight against insecurity in Nigeria and bring an end to Boko Haram terrorism, activities of bandits, farmers-herders conflicts, kidnapping among others, that have led to the loss of jobs and are discouraging foreign direct investments in the country
- Introduction of Entrepreneurship and Vocational Skill acquisition programs into school curricula such that self-employment can be guaranteed after school. This is one that has been embraced keenly in recent years as entrepreneurship is now a new subject in almost every university

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